

Cationic micelle induced reaction kinetic on de-phosphorylation of substituted mono phenyl phosphate ester in borate buffers of pH 8.0 to 10.0

S. S. Yadav* and Adesh Kumar

Department of Chemistry, Government Raza P. G. College, Rampur-244 901, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : bhadanaadesh@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 9 November 2006, revised 7 May 2007, accepted 18 July 2007

Abstract : Hydrolysis of mono 4-methyl phenyl phosphate and 4-ethyl phenyl phosphate ester has been studied with CTAB, a cationic surfactant at 40 ± 1.0 °C in borate buffers solutions of pH = 8.0, 9.0 and 10.0. Absorbances of them were measured spectrophotometrically and used to calculate rate constant of the hydrolysis, which found to be pseudo-first order. The process was run with and without CTAB with K_{ψ} and K'_{ψ} as rate constants respectively and the concentration of phosphate was restricted to 5.0×10^{-4} mol dm $^{-3}$ and CTAB varied in between 0.2×10^{-3} to 2×10^{-3} mol dm $^{-3}$. Rate constants increase with concentrations of CTAB, giving as rate maximum $K_{\psi} = 67.3 \times 10^{-5}$ s $^{-1}$ at 18×10^{-3} mol dm $^{-3}$ CTAB and $K'_{\psi} = 58.3 \times 10^{-5}$ s $^{-1}$ at 16×10^{-3} mol dm $^{-3}$ CTAB respectively at pH = 8.0 and pH = 9.0 for dianions of 4-mpp. But 4-EPP giving as rate maximum $K'_{\psi} = 69.5 \times 10^{-5}$ s $^{-1}$ at 18×10^{-3} mol dm $^{-3}$ CTAB and $K'_{\psi} = 60.8 \times 10^{-5}$ s $^{-1}$ at 16×10^{-3} mol dm $^{-3}$ CTAB respectively at pH = 8.0 and pH = 9.0, it is concluded that the contribution of methylene group towards dephosphorylation has been found to be 2.2×10^{-5} s $^{-1}$ and 2.5×10^{-5} s $^{-1}$ with respect to 18×10^{-3} mol dm $^{-3}$ CTAB and 16×10^{-3} mol dm $^{-3}$. The values of ion exchange parameters calculated at pH 8.0 and 9.0 by using various ion exchange equation have been summarized and found m^3_{OH} (concentration of reaction ion in Stern layer) 0.14, 0.452. K_S (binding constant) in 10^3 mol dm $^{-3}$ is 1.06, 3.64. K_w (second order rate constant of water) in 10^5 mol dm $^{-3}$ s $^{-1}$ is 215, 396. $[OH^-_w]$ (ion concentration in water) in 10^3 mol dm $^{-3}$ is 3.76, 20.43. $[OH^-_m]$ (ion concentration in micelle) in 10^4 mol dm $^{-3}$ is 1.32, 3.70 at borate buffer 3.9×10^{-3} mol dm $^{-3}$ $[OH^-]$, 20.3×10^{-3} mol dm $^{-3}$ $[OH^-]$. Activation energy is 7.64 kcal/mol and entropy is 32.06 [- $\Delta S \pm$ (eu)] at pH = 8 and used borate buffer 3.9×10^{-3} mol dm $^{-3}$ $[OH^-]$.

Keywords : Ionic micelle, dephosphorylation.

Micelle effects represent the most prominent and extensively studied example of surfactant influence on the kinetics of organic reactions in water and aqueous organic mixture. These systems open wide prospects for controlling the rate of chemical transformation and the state of equilibria there in¹. In the present work we performed a detailed kinetic analysis

of nucleophilic cleavage of hygroscopic 4-mpp in presence of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, whose front part includes cetyl ammonium group in water at 40 ± 1.0 °C. Our study was aimed at establishing the nature of factor responsible for the high rates of these processes mainly changes of the reactivity in going from aqueous to micelle phase and effect

Fig. 1(a)

of reactant concentration in the micelle phase. Pseudo-first order rate constants have been determined at different pH of the reaction medium. The factors, that influence the rate of reaction, such as pH, substrate composition, $[OH^-]$ have been studied. Activation parameters have been determined in usual manners.

Results and discussion

The reaction of mono-phosphate ester was strongly catalyzed at different concentration of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB)² at which the pseudo-first order rate constants were obtained (Fig. 1(a)).

Rate constant increases with detergent concentration. The values are : 6.73×10^{-6} and 5.64×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ at 1.8 and 1.6 is used to convert rate constants MCTAB at pH 8 and 9 respectively.

The expression in absorbances,

$$K_{\psi} = 2.303/t \log [A_{\alpha}]/[A_{\alpha} - X_t] \quad (1)$$

The concentration of micellised surfactant ' D_n ' is that total of surfactant concentration less than that of monomeric surfactant concentration. Which is assumed to be given by critical micelle concentration (CMC)³, which proves that the equilibrium is maintained between substrate in micelle and water respectively. It is shown by following equation

$$K_{\psi} = \frac{K'_w + K'_m K_s ([C_D] - CMC)}{1 + K_s ([D_n] - CMC)} \quad (2)$$

where the value of K'_m can be obtained by analysing the variation of K_s with D_n ⁴ or by choosing conditions, such that substrate is essentially fully micellised surfactant is given by the following reaction.

$$D_n = C_D - CMC$$

where C_D is total concentration of the surfactant.

Following relation gives the concentration of the micelle (M).

$$[M] = \frac{C_D - CMC}{N}$$

$$K_{\psi} = \frac{K'_w + K'_m \left(\frac{K_s}{N}\right) (C_D - CMC)}{1 + \left(\frac{K_s}{N}\right) (C_D - CMC)} \quad (3)$$

where N is aggregation number and K_s is binding constant.

The above treatment assumes that only one substrate molecule is incorporated into such micelles ' D_n ' an assumption, which is reasonable when the micelles are in large excess over the substrate. It has been used successfully for a number of spontaneous reactions but can be applied in a simple way for many reactions, which involve an external ionic reagent. As the rate constant increases with detergent concentration, the approximations generally lead to the maxima in the plot⁵.

Whereas eq. (1) predicts a rate plateau. The rate maxima have been explained in terms of ionic deactivation by the micelles in favourable cases. The binding constant K_s can be obtained directly⁶ according to the relation.

$$K_s = N/(K'_m - K'_w) \times \text{slope } 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$$

The estimated value of $1/(K_{\psi} - K'_w)$ and $1/(C_D - CMC)$ allows the determination of the value of K'_m , the rate constant in micelle and the binding constant K'_s for the reaction of 4-mpp with $[OH^-]$. The value of aggregation number $N = 61$ is taken from literature.

Fig. 1(b)

The reaction rate and micelle concentration in borate buffer for 4-mpp at pH 8 and temp. 40 ± 1.0 °C, and the value of CMC is 80×10^{-5} mol. $K'_w = 8.11 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $N = 61$. Calculated value of binding constant $K'_s = 0.56 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $K'_m = 79.54 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the reaction of mono-4-mpp with $[\text{OH}^-]$ at pH = 8.0 and temp. 40 ± 1.0 °C. Estimated value of $(K_\psi - K'_w)/(K'_m - K_\psi)$ and $(C_D - \text{CMC})$ illustrates the treatment for the reaction of 4-mpp with $3.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} [\text{OH}^-]$, in solution of cationic CTAB micelle. The calculated value of $K'_s/N = 0.65 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ for $K'_s = 39.65 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Quantitative treatment of the micelle induced reaction of $3.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ NaOH with $5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ 4-mpp at pH = 8 and temp. 40 ± 1.0 °C (Fig. 2).

The micelle induced hydrolysis has been found that hydrolysis strongly dependent on the nature of the detergent. The initial counter ion presented in hydrolysis and "local concentration" of the system due is to the total ionic contents of relative ion in the micellar pseudo phase.

To analyse the interfacial effect of the reaction of the hydroxide ion with 4-mpp treatment of ion exchange in micellar solutions that explicitly considers the consequence of ion-ion exchange. This approach permits to analyse the effect that given experimental conditions will have on the concern and the kinetic behavior on exchangeable ionic reactants in micellar pseudo phase, because such effects have been found to be strongly dependent on the nature of the detergent head group, the total content of the system and the initial concentrations present. The rate constants of 4-mpp can be related to surfactant concentration in term of the distribution of reactants in micellar and aqueous pseudo phase ion exchange model, which have been represented previously by scheme.

Where the second order rate constants in each pseudo

phase have been determined by taking into consideration of first order rate constants for over all reactions given by eq. (2), where K'_w and K'_m are first order rate constants in aqueous and micellar pseudo phase respectively.

$$K_\psi = \frac{K'_w + K'_m K'_s [D_n]}{1 + K'_s [D_n]} \quad (4)$$

where K'_s is binding constant, D_n is concentration of micellified surfactant.

It is assumed that interaction of two, or more counter ion with anionic micelles is governed by ion exchange equilibrium.

The 'm' and 'w' are in parent these denote micellar and aqueous pseudo phase respectively. Equilibrium or ion exchange constant for $[\text{OH}^-]$ and $[\text{Br}^-]$ denoted by $K_{\text{Br}}^{\text{OH}}$. So, eq. (4) can be written as,

$$K_\psi = \frac{K'_w (\text{OH}^-)_w + K'_m K'_s m_{\text{OH}}^S [D_n]}{1 + K'_s [D_n]} \quad (6)$$

where m_{OH}^S is the concentration of the reaction ion in the micelle.

The fraction of head group $K_{\text{Br}}^{\text{OH}}$ and β are assumed to be neutralized by counter ion and may be treated as independent of nature or concentration of counter ions.

For a mixture of $[\text{OH}^-]$ and $[\text{Br}^-]$, β is identical with $m_{\text{OH}}^S + m_{\text{Br}}^S$, the concentration of $[\text{OH}^-]$ and $[\text{OH}^-]_w$ are expressed in term of total concentration in solution volume, so that $[\text{OH}^-]_m$ and $[\text{Br}^-]_m$ can be given by substituting the value of $[\text{OH}^-]_m$, $[\text{OH}^-]_w$, $[\text{Br}^-]_w$ and $[\text{Br}^-]_m$ in eq. (5), leads to eq. (9).

$$[\text{OH}^-]_m = [\text{OH}^-]_w - m_{\text{OH}}^S [D_n] \quad (7)$$

$$[\text{Br}^-]_m = [\text{Br}^-]_w + [\beta - m_{\text{OH}}^S] [D_n] \quad (8)$$

Fig. 2

Table 1

K_{Br}^{OH}	$[OH_T^-] \times 10^3$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[OH_m^-] \times 10^4$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[OH_w^-] \times 10^4$ (mol dm ⁻³)	m_{OH}^S	$K_s \times 10^3$ (mol dm ⁻³)
10	3.9	1.32	3.76	0.14	1.06
$K_m \times 10^4$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$K_w' \times 10^5$ (mol dm ⁻³)	β			
6.03	8.11	0.75			

Selecting the value of K_{Br}^{OH} and β as 10.0 and 0.75 respectively, m_{OH}^S has been calculated from the reaction at 3.9×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ $[OH^-]$, by the eq. (10).

$$[m_{OH}^S]^2 + m_{OH}^S \left[\frac{[OH_T^-] + K_{Br}^{OH} [Br^-]}{[K_{Br}^{OH} - 1] [D_n]} - \beta \right] + \frac{\beta [OH_T^-]}{[K_{Br}^{OH} - 1] [D_n]} = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{K_\psi - K_w'}{m_{OH}^S [D_n]} = K_m' K_s - K_s \frac{K_\psi}{m_{OH}^S} \quad (10)$$

Quantitative treatment of the ion exchange modes for treatment of rate constants and parameters by the relation between $(K_\psi - K_w')/m_{OH}^S$ and $-K_\psi/m_{OH}^S$ for the micelle induced reaction of 4-mpp with 3.9×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ in 10^3 (CTAB), at pH = 8.0 and temp. 40 ± 10 °C.

These results suggest that pseudo phase ion exchange model can be applied as a first approximation to reactions of dianions of 4-mpp with $[OH^-]$ in CTAB micelles.

Bi-molecular reaction of hydrophilic anionic nucleophilices $[OH^-]$ by hydroxylic solvents that strongly bind the hydrogen to dianion concentration of anions at the surface of cationic micelles on the Stern⁸ layer have been calculated from the following equation.

$$[OH_m^-] = 1.32 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$$

$$[Br_m^-] = 1.12 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$$

$$K_{Br}^{OH} = 10$$

The concentration of dianions of 4-mpp in micelles has been calculated from equation.

$$K_s = \frac{[4\text{-mpp}]_m}{[4\text{-mpp}]_w [D_n]}$$

which allow the determination of reaction substrate concentration of dianions of 4-mpp in aqueous and micellar pseudo phase as under.

$$[4\text{-mpp}]_w = 1.12 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$$

$$[4\text{-mpp}]_m = 1.32 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$$

Ion exchange parameters and second order rate constant for

the reaction of 4-mpp with $[OH^-]$ in micellar pseudo phase at pH = 8 and temp. 40 ± 1.0 °C.

The aryl part of 4-mpp dianion is deeply buried in interior of micelles and the phosphate dianions are suitable exposed to nucleophilic attack by $[OH^-]$ ion, which is present in lower concentration in the micelle. Beside this, the dianions of 4-mpp are relatively hydrophobic and polarisable anions bind to micelles by the specific interaction but coulombic binding is much important in binding of hydrophilic anions. The dianions of 4-mpp, which are not very hydrophilic but are polarisable, interact with oxygen linkage, present in zwitter ionic form of monoester, forming hydrogen bonded cyclic intermediates by entrap of $[OH^-]$ ion reducing the coulombic interaction considerable. This interaction by $[OH^-]$ ions in cationic micelles was ascribed to the higher surface charge density at cationic as compared with the anionic centres.

Table 2. Comparative isokinetic rate data for the hydrolysis of some phosphate monoesters VIA other di-negative species

Phosphate mono	Temp.	ΔE (kcal/mol)	Entropy $\Delta S^\ddagger$ (eu)	Bond fission
4-Chloro-3,5-dimethylphenyl	40	26.4	8.5	P-O
4-Chloro-3-methylphenyl	40	27.18	9.7	P-O
<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	98	20.6	26.92	P-O
<i>o</i> -Methoxy- <i>p</i> -methylphenyl	98	18.7	33	P-O
3,5-Dimethylphenyl	98	24.66	12	P-O
2,4-Dinitrophenyl	98	20.9	21.2	P-O
1-Nitro-2-naphthylphenyl	98	15.9	21.2	P-O
4-Nitro-1-naphthylphenyl	98	15.08	35.45	P-O
<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	99	22.89	19.4	P-O
Pentachlorophenyl	97	19.67	29.3	P-O
4-Methylphenyl	40	7.64	32.06	P-O

Experimental

4-Methylphenyl phosphate ester has been prepared by general method⁹ in which phosphorus oxytrichloride directly react with 4-methylphenyl. The product always contains a mixture of mono-, di- and tri-esters. Di- and tri-esters are extracted with ether solvent and obtained mono ester. The above mono ester was identified analytically by IR spectral studies and kinetic studies have been done spectrophotometrically. Thermofegan RX100 IR spectrophotometer was used for above experimental work.

We used ammonium molybdate solution (8.3%), amidol reagent, hydrogen phosphate reagent. Amidol reagent used after purification and preparation. The amidol solution gradually decomposes, so fresh purified amidol solution was prepared when required. The borate buffer solution was prepared in double distilled water and 5×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ solution of the compound mono ester were always prepared. Aliquots measuring 5.0 ml were withdrawn from each run at definite intervals of time 25 ml standard flask which was immediately chilled in ice cold water to check further hydrolysis. For this 2.0 ml of amidol reagent and 1 ml of ammonium molybdate solution were introduced and total volume made up to mark in 50 ml standard flask by distilled water. After 7 min absorbances of fully developed blue colour was measured by spectrophotometer.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Prof. R. C. Sharma, Head, Department of Chemistry, Institute of Basic Sciences, Khandari, Agra University, Agra for providing necessary facilities and Dr. Pratibha Singh for giving valuable suggestions.

References

1. K. J. Mysels and P. Mukherjee, "Micellization, Solubilization and Microemulsions", ed. K. L. Mittal, New York, Plenum, 1977, (Translated under the title Mitselloobrazovanie, solyubilizatsiya i mikroemul' sii, Moscow, Mir, 1980, p. 11-31); C. A. Bunton, *Catal. Rev. Sci. Eng.*, 1979, **20**, 11; C. A. Bunton, F. Nome, L. R. Romsted and F. H. Quina, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1991, **24**, 357.
2. M. Patra and B. K. Sinha, *J. Micro. Sci. Part A : Pure and App. Chem.*, 2004, **37**, 1601.
3. F. M. Monger and C. E. Protoy, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 4698; C. A. Bunton and S. L. Jungger, *J. Am. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans.*, 1984, **2**, 355.
4. E. V. Cordes and R. B. Duntop, *J. Am. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans.*, 1969, **2**, 329; C. A. Bunton and B. Wolfe, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **96**, 7747; C. A. Bunton, F. Rivera and L. Sepuveda, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1978, **43**, 1166; C. A. Bunton, L. A. Romsted and H. J. Smith, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1978, **43**, 4299.
5. T. C. Bruice, in "The Enzyme", 3rd ed., Academic Press, New York, 1970, **2**, 217.
6. C. A. Bunton, L. Robinson, L. Sepulveda and M. J. Stem, *Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **92**, 1072.
7. G. P. J. Panigrahi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 58.
8. D. Stigter, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, **68**, 3603; K. Malinek, A. K. Yatsimirski, A. V. Laveshav and T. V. Berzin, "Micellization, Solubilization and Microemulsions", ed. K. L. Mittal, Plenum Press, New York, 1977, **2**.
9. T. Lovis, Gunkel, Crosby John (FML crop.) Eur. pats. Appl. 17 Aug. 1988, p. 276, 353; Appl. 09 Feb. 1984, **12**, p. 417.